

Extended Special Relativity (Part I)

Alex Kapanadze

ABSTRACT

In this two-part paper Einstein's Theory of Special Relativity is extended to incorporate gravity without invoking Einstein's Theory of General Relativity.

Part I introduces a connection between the energy differences among the reference frames and the magnitude of the associated relativistic effects. This connection is then used to bring the gravitational potential energy directly into the framework of the Special Relativity.

Part II is dedicated to describing how energy and matter affect space and time and vice-versa.

Keywords: Special Relativity, Gravity, Time dilation, Schwarzschild Metric, Black hole, Event horizon.

INTRODUCTION

The relative velocities between different frames of reference represent the very foundation of Einstein's theory of Special Relativity.

In this paper we are going to look closer at these velocity differences and explore their connection to something more fundamental – the energy.

RELATIVITY, VELOCITY, ENERGY AND GRAVITY

The key equation that is used in calculating the magnitude of the relativistic effects in Special Relativity is the Lorentz Factor equation:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (1)$$

Where γ is the Lorentz Factor (later referred to as the relativistic factor), v is the velocity of the moving frame of reference and c is the speed of light in the vacuum. From this equation we can say that the closer the velocity v is to the speed of light, the greater the magnitude of the Lorentz Factor, as well as the magnitude of the relativistic effects such as the length contraction, time dilation and the relativistic mass gain. These calculations are done from the point of view of the observer in the stationary frame of reference.

Let us now take a closer look at the moving frame of reference.

There is a property in Special Relativity that is associated with the moving reference frames called Celerity. Celerity (w) is a velocity that is determined by the following equation:

$$w = \frac{dx}{d\tau} \quad (2)$$

where dx represents the displacement of the moving reference frame (moving observer) inside the stationary reference frame and $d\tau$ is the time interval that this displacement took as measured by the moving observer's clock (proper time). The celerity has a special meaning for the moving observer as it represents the velocity with which this observer is advancing through the space of the stationary reference frame. From the point of view of the moving observer everything in the stationary reference frame is subjected to the relativistic effects such as the length contraction and the time dilation, however, they themselves, within the moving frame of reference, would be immune to these affects. Furthermore, they will find that they can keep increasing their velocity (celerity) though the stationary reference frame with no limit. Regardless of the magnitude of this velocity, the mass of any objects in the moving reference frame will remain invariant and the flow of time (locally) will remain unaffected.

We can say that by referencing the displacement in the stationary reference frame against the passage of time

in the moving reference frame we have exposed the Newtonian foundation of the Special Relativity. This is underscored by the following relativistic equation:

$$v = \frac{w}{\gamma} \quad (3)$$

which tells us that the relativistic velocity of the moving frame of reference, as seen by the stationary observer (v), can be determined by dividing the underlying, non-relativistic (Newtonian) velocity (w) by the relativistic Lorentz Factor (γ).

If we now express v in terms of w using (3) then the equation (1) will look like this:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{w^2}{c^2}}} \quad (4)$$

which can be transformed into this:

$$\frac{1}{\gamma^2} = 1 - \frac{w^2}{c^2} \quad (5)$$

and finally the following:

$$\gamma^2 c^2 = c^2 + w^2 \quad (6)$$

We can also replace the w^2 term in (6) with the non-relativistic kinetic energy per unit of mass (k) as follows:

$$\gamma^2 c^2 = c^2 + 2k \quad (7)$$

where:

$$k = \frac{1}{2} w^2 \quad (8)$$

This Newtonian kinetic energy can be looked at in terms of work, allowing us to make the following statement:

(Statement 1)

The magnitude of the relativistic factor between a stationary inertial reference frame and a moving reference frame is a function of the amount of work

needed to bring the celerity velocity of a unit of mass to 0, as measured in the moving reference frame, attached to the unit of mass.

The exact dependence can be expressed by the following set of equations:

$$\gamma = \sqrt{1 + \frac{2k}{c^2}} \quad (9)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2k}{\gamma^2 c^2}}} \quad (10)$$

The (Statement 1) relates only to the Newtonian kinetic energy. However, the non-relativistic potential energy (Newtonian gravity) can also be directly converted to the change in velocity or the kinetic energy, opening the door to including the gravity in the relativistic factor calculations.

The gravitational potential energy conversion directly to the kinetic energy can be illustrated by a stationary observer falling toward a mass from a far away point where the mass has no influence.

It is important to note that the velocity of the observer as they fall toward the mass, will be measured from the point of view of the falling observer, as the displacement in the stationary frame of reference divided by the proper time interval of the falling observer (celerity).

If we refer to the initial distance of the observer from the mass as r_∞ , the initial celerity velocity of the observer as w_∞ , and refer to a point located much closer to the mass as r , then the celerity velocity (w) that this free falling observer will obtain by the time they reach the point r can be calculated using the following equation:

$$w = \sqrt{w_\infty^2 + \frac{2GM}{r} - \frac{2GM}{r_\infty}} \quad (11)$$

Since $w_\infty = 0$ and $r_\infty = \infty$, the equation (11) can be written in the following form:

$$w^2 = \frac{2GM}{r} \quad (12)$$

If we now take into account that:

$$\Phi = \frac{GM}{r} \quad (13)$$

where Φ is the Newtonian gravitational potential energy per unit of mass, then we can rewrite (12) as:

$$w^2 = 2\Phi \quad (14)$$

Now we can combine equations (12) and (14) with the equation (4) to derive the following relativistic factor calculation equations:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2\Phi}{\gamma^2 c^2}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{\gamma^2 r c^2}}} \quad (15)$$

$$\gamma = \sqrt{1 + \frac{2\Phi}{c^2}} = \sqrt{1 + \frac{2GM}{r c^2}} \quad (16)$$

At this point, the relationship between the Newtonian gravitational potential energy and the relativistic factor can be summarized in the following statement:

(Statement 2)

The magnitude of the relativistic factor between a stationary inertial reference frame and a target reference frame affected by a nearby mass is a function of the amount of work needed to move a unit of mass from the point affected by the mass, to the location of the stationary inertial reference frame, as measured in the target reference frame attached to the unit of mass.

From the equations (10) and (15) we can see that it does not matter if the nature of the energy difference between the reference frames is potential or kinetic. As long as the amount of energy difference is the same, the magnitude of the relativistic effects will also be the same.

From the same two equations we can also see that the “raw”, unlimited Newtonian kinetic and potential energies per unit of mass are being mitigated by the relativistic factor. Resulting in the following conditions:

$$\frac{2k}{\gamma^2} \leq c^2 \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{2\Phi}{\gamma^2} \leq c^2 \quad (18)$$

As a result, the following statement can be made:

(Statement 3)

No object in any reference frame can possess a specific energy greater than c^2 .

The combined magnitude of relativistic effects is the product of the relativistic effects produced by the kinetic and potential energies. By combining the equations (1) and (16) we can produce a common relativistic factor equation:

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{c^2 + 2\Phi}{c^2 - v^2}} \quad (19)$$

COMPARISON WITH THE SCHWARZSCHILD METRIC

The gravitational time dilation calculation equation derived from the Schwarzschild metric looks like this:

$$\frac{\Delta t'}{\Delta t} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{r_0 c^2}} \quad (20)$$

Where the time intervals $\Delta t'$ and Δt refer to the duration of a single event measured by two observers. One observer is affected by the gravitational acceleration (located at r_0 , measuring $\Delta t'$) and the other one is not (located far away, measuring Δt).

The equation (15), derived in this paper, adapted to the same format, will look like this:

$$\frac{\Delta t'}{\Delta t} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{\gamma^2 r_0 c^2}} \quad (21)$$

Unlike the equation (21), the equation (20) derived from the Schwarzschild Metric, brings an unmitigated Newtonian specific potential energy into the calculation. This has a dramatic effect on the time

dilation calculations. The differences between the two methods are very obvious in the chart below:

Fig.1

We can clearly see that the Schwarzschild equation has an asymptote at 2 (Schwarzschild radius), leading to the creation of an event horizon and a singularity at that point.

In contrast, the equation (16) has an asymptote at 0 (central singularity), and is continuous throughout the domain of the function. Nothing special happens at the Schwarzschild radius.

CONCLUSIONS

Considering the energy differences between the reference frames allowed us to create a direct link between the Theory of Special Relativity and gravity.

We have derived new equations for calculating the magnitude of the relativistic effects caused by the gravitational potential energy.

The results obtained from these new equations are drastically different from the results rendered by the Schwarzschild Metric equations. Especially when it comes to the very strong gravitational influences.

Here are just a few key consequences of the new approach:

- The flow of time does not stop anywhere outside the central singularity of the *Schwarzschild black hole*, as seen by an observer located anywhere outside the central singularity;
- A photon of any energy that is originated anywhere outside the central singularity can travel radially outward from the center of mass without limit and will be subjected only to a finite amount of the *gravitational redshift*;
- *Schwarzschild black holes* do not produce event horizons outside the central singularity.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Special thanks to Dr. Derek Muller for making inspiring Veritasium videos on the topic of Physics and Dr. Carl Rod Nave for creating and maintaining the free Hyper Physics resource.

REFERENCES